

Horizon 2020 Work programme

Food Security, Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry, Marine, Maritime and Inland Water Research and the Bioeconomy

Call

H2020-FNR-2020: Food and Natural Resources

Topic name

FNR-16-2020: ENZYMES FOR MORE ENVIRONMENT-FRIENDLY CONSUMER PRODUCTS

FuturEnzyme:

Technologies of the Future for Low-Cost Enzymes for Environment-Friendly Products

Final ID: 101000327

31/05/2024

NEWSDIGEST, POSTERS, BULLETINS

D8.8

MANUEL FERRER

CSIC

MARIE CURIE 2, 28049 CANTOBLANCO, MADRID, SPAIN

Document information sheet

Work package:	WP8, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Authors:	CSIC (Manuel Ferrer, Patricia Molina)
Document version:	1
Date:	31/05/2024
WP starting date:	01/06/2021
WP duration:	48 months
WP lead beneficiary:	ITB
WP participant(s):	CSIC as main contributor and all partners for providing feedback and suggestions for implementation
Deliv lead beneficiary:	CSIC
Dissemination Level:	Public
Type	Websites, patents filling, etc.
Due date (months)	36
Contact details:	Manuel Ferrer (mferrer@icp.csic.es)

Summary

NEWSDIGEST, POSTERS, BULLETINS.....	4
1. Scope of deliverable	4
2. Roll-up.....	4
3. Posters and banners	5
4. Newsletter	7
5. Brochures.....	9
6. Comic.....	10
7. Video.....	11
8. Conclusions.....	12

NEWSDIGEST, POSTERS, BULLETINS

1. Scope of deliverable

This deliverable, developed in M36, summarizes the communication materials for disseminating and communicating project objectives and outcomes for stakeholders, SMEs and industries operating in the biotech sector as well as the scientific community and the general public. In particular, this deliverable includes the following:

- Roll-up.
- Poster.
- Newsletter in the form of LinkedIn editorials.
- Brochures (detailed information are reported in D8.7).
- Comic (detailed information are reported in D8.12).
- Video (detailed information are reported in D8.12).

Aligning with what is already reported in D8.7 *FuturEnzyme project leaflet and brochure*, the general objectives of this material are:

- To communicate the potential benefits of FuturEnzyme to multiple stakeholders.
- To increase project visibility at events and online.
- To provide concise information on project objectives and achievements.
- To exploit FuturEnzyme outputs and results.

Specific objectives, targeted stakeholders and the distribution channels for each material are detailed within this deliverable.

This material is available through the [website](#) and the official project communication channels ([LinkedIn](#) and [X](#)).

2. Roll-up

Objectives

A roll-up is used to attract people attention to the FuturEnzyme project at bigger events, such as fairs, and conferences, but it can be in general used for all the FuturEnzyme events to make the project easily recognizable from a long distance. It, thus, can be used for events with any type of stakeholders.

Content analysis

The roll-up is a self-sustaining canvas in which the main information on the FuturEnzyme project has been reported. In details, the roll-up reports:

- The project logo, acronym and full-title.
- The project original images (the general one e the three images for the three products).
- A summary of the project objectives.
- The logo of the EU, highlighting the funding information.
- Partners' logos.
- Project website and QR code linked with the project website.

The roll-up is in the 100x215 cm format size, but it can be easily adapted to make it compliant with different national editorial standards.

Distribution channels

The project roll-up was prepared in February 2023 to be used by CLIB to the CLIB International Conference (CIC) 2023 (**Figure 1**). In general, the project can be used at any events, conferences or fairs in which FuturEnzyme take part to.

Figure 1. Roll-up display at CIC2023

The roll-up is publicly available on the [project website](#) and [Zenodo](#).

3. Posters and banners

Objectives

The posters and banners summarize the main concept of the project and can be used to be displayed at conferences or events or during lab/facility visits. They can also be used as teaching or communication material for the general public.

Content analysis

The first project poster (**Figure 2**) was developed in May 2023 and it summarises the main benefits of the project for the three main targets: consumers, environment and companies. To make the poster easily recognizable, it also includes one of the main project original images, the project logo, full title and EU logo.

Figure 2. Simplified project poster

A more detailed version of the poster was also developed in November 2023, mainly intended to be used as a banner during fairs (Figure 3). Besides the basic information reported in the general poster, the banner also includes a summary of the project objectives and a focus on the three targeted products.

The banner is in a 240x100 cm format.

Figure 3. Project banner

Distribution channels

The general poster was prepared and used for the event “Engineering enzymes for consumer products of higher environmental quality (Workshop on Computational Enzyme Bioprospecting and Engineering, 22-23.05.2023, Barcelona, Spain) organized by partner BSC”, while the banner was prepared and used for the Ecomondo fair attended by ITB. The distribution channels for this material are mainly conferences, events and fairs, but can also be used internally to partners’ lab or as communication material.

The posters are available on the project website and [Zenodo](#).

4. Newsletter

Objectives

The “[Greening Thinking](#)”, the project newsletter issued on LinkedIn, is used to inform the public about how enzymes and the production of more sustainable products are essential to face today’s challenges. This newsletter gathers a series of editorial targeting different topics of doing research and of the enzyme world. It targets mainly researchers, students, and workers with a diverse background as well as the general public explaining the science behind FuturEnzyme and describing the main project achievements. FuturEnzyme editorials are not scientific articles but are contributions to the general audience to briefly inform and raise the attention on certain topics of the readers.

Content analysis

Figure 4. Newsletter logo

The project newsletter, called the **Greening Thinking**, is in the form of LinkedIn editorials that are issued monthly through the project LinkedIn social account. Each editorial is about 4.000 characters long and is curated by one of the project partners. Each partner contributes to at least one editorial based on their area of expertise, with the coordination of ITB, as the communication and dissemination leader, and CSIC, as the project coordinator.

The newsletter has been active since July 2023, currently counts 380 subscribers, 2538 views, and 185 of interactions (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Number of views of the newsletter "The Greening Thinking". Views peaks can be observed monthly corresponding to the publication of a new issue

11 issues have been already published. Topics of the published issues are detailed in the table below:

Title	Partner	Publication date	Link
Sustainable consumer products: is there a gap between consumer attitudes and shopping behaviours?	ITB	20/07/2023	Link
Implementing Responsible Research and Innovation for a greener Europe	CSIC/ITB	22/08/2023	Link
Greener consumer goods need Responsible Research & Innovation	CSIC/ITB	20/09/2023	Link
Artificial Intelligence at the service of enzymatic every-day consumer products	BSC	23/10/2023	Link
Navigating from Abyss to Antarctic in Search of Industrial Innovation - How to Choose Where to Go?	CNR	27/11/2023	Link
What does it take for an enzyme to be used in a detergent formulation?	HENKEL	20/12/2023	Link
Pioneering a Chemical-Free Revolution using Enzymes in the textile manufacturing process	SCHOELLER	23/01/2024	Link
Enzymes in the cosmetic industry	EVONIK	26/02/2024	Link
Unleashing the Power of Cell-Free Expression: Revolutionizing Enzyme Discovery for Industry	UHAM	26/03/2024	Link
Innovating products for consumers demands cutting-edge analytics	IST-ID	24/04/2024	Link
Bridging innovation: how industry-university collaborations can fuel technological advancements for enzymes design and development	BIOSYNTH	27/05/2024	Link

In total, around 25 editorials are expected by the end of the project. Next topics are expected to include the following:

- Scaling up of native expression hosts, expected for June 2024.
- How to find the right enzyme, expected for July 2024.
- High-throughput enzyme screening, expected for August 2024.
- Potential of immobilised enzymes for industrial applications, expected for September 2024.
- LCA of benchmark products, expected for October 2024.

- Collaboration within institutions as the key to overcome global challenges, expected for November 2024.
- Enzymes smart design, expected for December 2024.

The above list is a draft of possible next issues for the FuturEnzyme newsletter. However, based on the project results, the publication order and topics may change. As example, in the third General Assembly meeting, it was agreed upon the possibility for members of the Advisory Board to contribute. Furthermore, the last issues for 2025 still needs to be planned according to the main results that the project will achieve in the upcoming months.

Distribution channels

The newsletter is distributed on LinkedIn, in association with the FuturEnzyme [Linkelin social media page](#), which counts over than 679 followers. Combining the newsletter with social media proved to be an effective strategy for increasing the number of subscribers and readers.

To increase the newsletter visibility, the project website has a direct [link](#) to the subscription page.

5. Brochures

Objectives

The general objectives of FuturEnzyme brochures are:

- To communicate the potential benefits of FuturEnzyme to multiple stakeholders;
- To increase project visibility at events and online;
- To provide concise information on project objectives and achievements;
- To exploit FuturEnzyme outputs and results.

The brochures specific objectives are detailed in **D8.7**

Content analysis

Four different brochures (front page in **Figure 6**) were prepared in April 2022 to target the different needs and expectations of the various target groups of the FuturEnzyme project:

1. **FuturEnzyme, a project meeting costumers' demand.** This brochure is dedicated to consumers, analysing the trends and requests in the detergent, cosmetic and textile sectors and how the project is committed to meeting consumers' demand.
2. **FuturEnzyme project: who will benefit?** This brochure, dedicated to consumers, describes the positive impact of the FuturEnzyme project on consumers, companies, and the planet.
3. **Enzymes for sustainable everyday products: benefits and challenges.** This brochure is dedicated to academia as it provides more information on the potential benefits of using enzymes and insights on how the FuturEnzyme project is committed to overcoming the major challenges associated with discovering enzymes, with a focus on the bioprospecting platform.
4. **FuturEnzyme project: new consumer products for the green transition of European industries:** dedicated to industries, this last brochure analyses the main technological and environmental challenges associated with manufacturing consumer products and, thus, highlight how enzymes could improve the impact of these products, particularly how they can provide a bridge between circular economy and climate change mitigation.

Brochures incorporate the colours and figures of the already established project visual identity, including the project logo and original images and using the same colour palette. A strong visual identity makes the project recognisable at events, conferences, and online such as on social media, representing and differentiating FuturEnzyme initiatives at the international level.

Figure 6. Project brochures. Starting from the top left corner: consumers (1,2); academia (3); industry (4)

Distribution channels

The main distribution channel for brochures dissemination is **social media**. The A5-slide format of brochures is suitable for sharing the brochures on social media both as downloadable materials and as single specific posts. All brochures were disseminated through social media between April and July 2022.

Brochures are also available in a printable booklet format that can be used for distribution at any types of events.

Other distribution channels for FuturEnzyme brochures include [project website](#) (where it is possible to download all the brochures), [Zenodo](#), and emails to partners and collaborators.

6. Comic

Objectives

By summarizing the main concept of the project in the form of a cartoon, the project comic is intended to maximize the FuturEnzyme dissemination and communication impact towards a broad audience. The comic aims to raise awareness on the importance of using enzymes in consumers products to reduce their environmental footprint, while providing some insights into how enzymes are discovered and produced. The comic is particularly useful for dissemination towards children and students as well as consumers in general that do not have a technical or scientific background.

Content analysis

The comic, published in October 2023, is composed of 13 strips designed by Ainhoa Quiros (front page in **Figure 7**). Being the same illustrator of already produced visual identity and material of the FuturEnzyme project, the designer ensured that all the visual elements of the project were included in the comic, ensuring that the material is easily recognized by the stakeholders.

Figure 7. First strip of the FuturEnzyme comic

Regarding the topics presented, the comic includes the following:

- Introduction on the importance of enzymes in fighting the climate change.
- How to find and produce enzymes: from the bioprospecting in underexplored environments to the pre-industrial enzymatic production.
- How enzymes can be incorporated into consumers products, mainly cosmetics, laundry detergents and textiles.
- The last page also contains the logos of all the project partners as well as the EU logo to acknowledge for funding.

More details on the comics are available in D8.12.

Distribution channels

The comic is mainly intended for online distribution through the [project website](#) and [social media](#) platforms, where it already reached over 1000 views. A printable version is also available for all the partners in order to bring printed copies to events and schools. The printed comic was presented at the Ecomondo Fair, the CIC2024, the Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival, and the Europe Day at the Eugenio Trias Library, with over 200 copies distributed.

7. Video

Objectives

Similar to the comic, the project video aims to disseminate the project objectives, workflow and targets to a broader audience, including consumers that do not have a technical or scientific background. The video can be used at conferences, events or even as teaching materials in schools.

Content analysis

The video, published in September 2023, is a realistic animated video created by [Design Cells](#) (a screenshot on the animated video in **Figure 8**). The video, lasting 3 minutes and 30 seconds, is composed of 5 parts that can be used combined or separate to make for example, more effective posts on social media.

Figure 8. A screenshot of the video

The video is structured in order to include: an introduction part on the issues in our current production and consumption models; three sections for each product; one final scene on the objectives of the FuturEnzyme project. More details on the video are described in D8.12.

Distribution channels

The video is intended for online distribution through [social media](#) and [project websites](#). It can also be shown at conferences/events during presentations or as teaching materials in schools, such as in the CIC2024.

8. Conclusions

In brief, this deliverable covers different multi-media materials designed to boost FuturEnzyme's reach, so our project can get to all types of audiences using adequate formats for each one and for the different events or activities the project participates.

This document is available in the website intranet of the project (see www.futureenzyme.eu -> login -> private-area -> DELIVERABLES & MILESTONES -> DELIVERABLES -> D8.8_Newsdigest, posters, buletins).